

OPEN SCIENCE NL

Work programme 2026–2027

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Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië 300
2593 CE Den Haag
www.openscience.nl

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Illustration page 6: Alicia Dekker/Open Science NL

Printwork: Quantes Grafimedia, Rijswijk

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Please cite as

Open Science NL (2025). Open Science NL work programme 2026–2027. Open Science NL.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17579089>

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Introduction

Background

Open Science NL has been set up within the Dutch Research Council (NWO) on the initiative of the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science in order to accelerate the implementation of open science in the Netherlands. One of the key tasks of Open Science NL is to “identify, prioritise, and fund temporary initiatives and projects for sustainable Open Science embedding, based on the NPOS 2030 Ambition Document”.

Open Science NL outlines its funding initiatives through its work programmes, which are published every two years. This work programme 2026-2027 is the second work programme of Open Science NL¹.

Community consultation and prioritisation

Open Science NL uses the National Programme Open Science (NPOS) 2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda² (hereafter: the NPOS Ambition) as the overall framework for the development of its work

programmes and financial instruments. The NPOS Ambition sets out 30 objectives, while community needs continue to evolve and take into account new developments and challenges such as concerns around AI and open science or digital sovereignty in key open science infrastructures. To identify and prioritise funding needs, Open Science NL therefore relies on community consultation in line with its Community Engagement Strategy³. This prioritisation was especially important in preparing the 2026-2027 work programme, given the 50% budget reduction for Open Science NL by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. Although part of the cut was mitigated by additional funding from NWO in recognition of the importance of the open science transition, the overall budget remains lower than in the 2024-2025 work programme.

In the process of developing the work programme 2026-2027, community consultation workshops were e.g. organised during the October 2024 Open Science Festival, with key insights documented in publicly available blog posts⁴.

¹The first work programme of Open Science NL, the Open Science NL - Work programme 2024-2025 has been published in 2023 and is publicly available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10074873>

²NPOS. (2022). Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda (Approved version). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

³Open Science NL. (2023). Open Science NL Community engagement strategy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16563295>.

⁴[Workshop report: Designing the Work Programme 2026-2027: Data, Software and Hardware](#), [Workshop recap: Citizen Science & Societal Engagement for Open Science NL](#), [Workshop report: Designing the Work Programme 2026-2027: Open Scholarly Communication](#)

[Open Science NL expert advisory panels](#) then reviewed the community suggestions, providing in-depth feedback that informed further discussions with the Steering Board. The Steering Board then gave its final approval of the work programme.

The mapping between the proposed initiatives, the objectives of the NPOS Ambition and the outcomes of community consultation is provided in [Annex 1](#).

Structure

Culture change to open science requires a comprehensive approach that addresses both technical and social dimensions. Therefore, all funding ideas described in this work programme are structured around five main themes essential for the transition to open science:

1. Infrastructure
2. Capacity building
3. Empowering communities
4. Incentives
5. Monitoring and evaluation

These five themes are inspired by and can be mapped to the components of the Strategy for Culture Change outlined by Brian Nosek⁵.

The choice of this specific framework is not motivated by scientific evidence, but by two practical reasons:

1. to aid the mapping to the NPOS Ambition where this framework was used to formulate the key requirements for the transition to open science;
2. to facilitate international conversations and alignment, where this framework is often used as a reference.

Furthermore, it should also be noted that while the original components were structured in the form of a pyramid, Open Science NL perceives all five components as equally important for the transition to open science.

⁵ Blog post by Brian Nosek "[Strategy for Culture Change](#)"

Infrastructure provides the tools, platforms and workflows that make practising open science technically possible. **Capacity building** ensures that practitioners have the knowledge and skills to apply open science practices and to use infrastructure effectively and are supported in these processes. **Incentives** align recognition and rewards with open practices, signalling that these behaviours are valued. **Empowering communities** creates peer-driven norms where openness is expected. Finally, **monitoring and evaluation** set clear expectations, enable progress tracking, and help embedding open science in a sustained manner.

Eligibility

The outline of each of the anticipated funding instrument in this work programme indicate who the eligible applicants are. In the context of this work programme, the term “knowledge institutions” means all institutions listed in the NWO Grant Rules (universities, university medical centres, universities of applied sciences, KNAW and NWO institutes and a few other organisations).

Open science principles and intellectual property

Unless specified otherwise, recipients of Open Science NL funding are obliged to follow NWO's grant rules with regard to intellectual

property (IP) management and must ensure that any research outputs are made publicly available. Specifically, the recipients must comply with the NWO research data management policy and NWO open access policy.

Assessment of proposals

Assessment procedures for the various initiatives proposed in this work programme will be developed as funding instruments (e.g. calls for proposals or tenders) are being drafted.

1 Infrastructure

The two initiatives described in this chapter are related to creating tools, infrastructures and workflows which enable open science practices.

1.1 Open Science Infrastructure

Why

Open science infrastructure plays an essential role in enhancing the accessibility, transparency, and reproducibility of scientific research and outputs. The 2024 round of the **Open Science Infrastructure** Call for proposals attracted numerous strong proposals, revealing significant demand for both discipline-specific and domain-agnostic platforms, tools, and integrations. The popularity of the call highlighted the importance of this funding instrument and the need to launch another Call for proposals addressing open science infrastructure needs.

What

The high competition among excellent proposals in 2024 round of the **Open Science Infrastructure** call indicated a need for a more targeted approach. This Call for proposals will aim to:

1. focus on specific, prioritised needs of the broad research community;
2. foster greater collaboration between institutions, projects and infrastructures, stimulate interoperability between infrastructures and reduce duplication of efforts;

3. support strategic development of digitally-sovereign open science infrastructure in alignment with national and European initiatives;
4. balance support for both discipline-specific solutions and domain-agnostic platforms, tools and services;
5. strive for a higher success rate (at least 25%), in line with NWO's Strategy 2023-2026.

The exact mechanisms for achieving these aims are still being discussed and will be specified further in the Call for proposals.

In addition, coordination activities aiming to stimulate collaboration and facilitate consortia-building around similar initiatives in order to reduce the duplication of efforts might be funded alongside the Call for proposals (from the same budget).

Financial instrument

Call for proposals. Coordination activities, if awarded, will be funded through a direct grant or a tender.

Eligibility

Call for proposals: researchers and professional support staff affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions.

Coordination activities: direct grant/tender to the most suitable organisation.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

While Open Science NL's Infrastructure programme is the only dedicated funding opportunity for open science infrastructure in the Netherlands, other NWO funding programmes, such as [Research Infrastructure: national consortia](#), [Large-Scale Infrastructures](#), or [Thematic Digital Competence Centers](#) or the National Growth Fund can also fund open digital infrastructure.

Budget

€17.5M in 2027.

1.2 Improving access to sensitive data

Why

Sensitive data (for example personal, medical, commercial or environmental data) can only be shared if safeguards such as legally binding agreements, anonymisation or controlled analysis environments are in place. Because data access conditions and procedures are not standardised, they are complex to specify and hard to understand. Furthermore, they are time-consuming and therefore costly to execute for both data providers and users. This affects researchers, practitioners, and citizens that need access to such data, limiting research, innovation, and public engagement.

Two important international efforts are underway (the World Wide Web Consortium's ODRL⁶ and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health passport/DUO suite⁷) to allow

comprehensive, machine-actionable specification of access conditions, which helps to standardise the access process for all types of data. Implementation of these developing standards has the potential to simplify the process of getting access to sensitive data. However, understanding and implementing a standard requires a coordinated effort: uptake is not guaranteed by the availability of a trustworthy technical solution.

What

Crucial factors in uptake are consensus, the availability of technical expertise, and the capacity to undertake the implementation effort. To facilitate and stimulate these, it is proposed to fund:

- National coordination and implementation support: overall alignment and coordination effort through domain-specific support/coordination capacity and a dedicated implementation expert that will support applicants of the implementation grants (3 years, €1.1M)
- Implementation grants (28 grants of €50K for a maximum project length of 1.5 years)

The implementation grants will provide for a critical mass of early adopters: a first push that can cause a snowball effect. The implementation grants will be started after the launch of the national coordination project, to ensure that projects receive sufficient support during the implementation. Funding for implementation grants will be split between the different domains of research.

⁶The Open Digital Rights Language, see <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ODRL> and <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

⁷See <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/ga4gh-passports/> and <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/>

Financial instrument

- **National coordination:** direct grant.
- **Implementation grants:** Call for proposals.

Eligibility

- Direct grant to the most suitable institution to lead the national coordination project.
- **Implementation grants:** to be determined.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

Large data providers (organisations such as CBS, ODISSEI and Health-RI) have undertaken efforts towards standardisation of processes and licenses within their own organisations or domain. The next step is to start working on a more common approach, which requires a nationally coordinated effort, to bridge the domains and stimulate implementation, while at the same time aligning with international developments. Such an effort does not yet exist.

Budget

€1.1M in 2026 and €1.4M in 2027.

2 Capacity building

The four instruments described in this chapter are aimed at helping the community increase the skills and experience needed to embrace open science practices.

2.1 Training for open science infrastructure sustainability

Why

The sustainability of open science infrastructure is a complex and multifaceted challenge. These infrastructures form the backbone of an open and collaborative research ecosystem – yet their long-term survival is often not guaranteed, which has been brought to light even more in the current geo-political climate. Many valuable initiatives depend on precarious funding, volunteer efforts, or short-term projects, making them vulnerable. Ensuring that open science infrastructure remains resilient over time requires more than technical excellence. While those responsible for open science infrastructures often excel in innovation and problem-solving – skills essential for building them – they frequently lack the expertise needed for ensuring long-term sustainability, such as developing and implementing viable funding models. This initiative seeks to address that skills gap.

What

This instrument offers funding for the development and subsequent delivery

of a sustainability training for those responsible for open science infrastructure in all lifecycle stages, focusing on three main areas:

- 1. Core strategic skills** – including the ability to understand and address stakeholder and user needs (and involve them where relevant), as well as expertise in governance, operations, finance and funding, resource planning, and marketing.
- 2. Technology best practices** – covering principles of usability, sustainability, effective implementation, and user-centred design tailored to open science digital environments.
- 3. Long-term sustainability strategies** – such as exploring alternative funding models, developing integration approaches, learning from case studies of successful initiatives, as well as considering how to secure the legacy of discontinued infrastructures.

The aim is to propose a way to sustain this training within the Dutch research ecosystem.

Financial instrument

A direct grant or procurement.

Eligibility

Direct grant or procurement to the most suitable organisation.

Training will be open to researchers and professional support staff affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions, who are responsible for open science infrastructures.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

There is currently no comparable training and learning programme in the Netherlands focused on making open science infrastructure sustainable. A comparable programme has been set up in Australia and relevant resources have been developed by [the EC-funded project Managing the Lifecycle of an RI](#).

Both can serve as good practices and as a starting point for this instrument. Furthermore, training on sustainability and digital sovereignty of academic infrastructures was organised in the past by SURF for those in leadership positions in academia (no reference available).

Budget

€250K in 2026.

2.2 Mobility and development programme

Why

Open science roles – such as data stewards, research software engineers, community managers, open scholarly publishing experts, open research hardware engineers, and citizen science specialists – are still relatively new. For most of these positions, no official training programmes exist to provide those interested with the necessary skills and experience. Moreover, open science professionals have limited opportunities to learn from each other, particularly across borders, and to share good practices.

What

Open science professionals will be able to apply for dedicated funding (up to €25K) to develop transferable skills through structured study visits. Each visit must have a clear programme, a well-defined rationale, and confirmed commitment from all participating parties. Funding may be used to cover the fellow's expenses during the visit (including travel), to release the applicant's time to participate or to release the capacity of the host to ensure adequate involvement of the host in the programme. Applicants must also outline how the knowledge and skills gained will be shared and embedded within their home organisation and/or the wider open science community.

Both starting and experienced open science professionals who want to learn new skills or gain new professional experience are the intended audience for this call for proposals.

Funding instrument

First come, first served Call for proposals. Potentially the call can be split into two rounds.

Eligibility

Open science professionals (individuals or teams) affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions. Hosting organisations can be any non-commercial organisations.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives?

There are two other programmes which offer support for mobility:

- NWO Rubicon is a mobility programme for long term research projects abroad (postdoc), usually lasting for about 2 years.

These are research focussed, long-lasting and not dedicated to open science.

- Erasmus+ is an exchange programme for staff and higher education institutions to undertake training in other countries in Europe and elsewhere. Individuals are not eligible to apply for these grants – applications can only be made once per year by institutions. Institutions are also tasked with organising the internal selection and administering the grants.

The programme funded by Open Science NL is the only programme offering mobility support dedicated to open science. The programme is not dedicated to open science.

Budget

€1M in 2026.

2.3 Open research hardware network

Why

Open research hardware⁸ is an essential pillar of open science. Sharing research hardware designs openly enables more people within and outside of academia to access, replicate, modify and use the hardware. A rapidly increasing volume of research contains open research hardware, but the number of scientific publications on this topic is trailing that of open-source software with a lag of roughly 15 years. There is large-scale open research hardware development worldwide, and there are bottom-up open research

hardware developments in the Netherlands. However, within the Dutch community there is comparatively little awareness and coordination on this topic.

What

This initiative aims to provide funding for four years for the establishment of an open research hardware network in the Netherlands. The network will be expected to:

- raise awareness about open research hardware;
- connect diverse communities which could benefit from working on/reusing open research hardware designs;
- provide training on making hardware designs open and FAIR;
- create networking opportunities and organise events and workshops on open research hardware;
- stimulate coordination on open research hardware within the Netherlands;
- establish connections with relevant national (e.g. open research software) and international networks (e.g. other open research hardware).

Funding instrument

Call for proposals.

Eligibility

Consortium of eligible knowledge institutions.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

While there are open hardware developments at individual institutions (e.g. TU Delft, the

⁸ Open research hardware refers to physical tools, instruments, devices etc. used for research that are developed and shared under open licences, allowing others to study, modify, build, and improve them. Examples, among many others, include open-source microscopes that anyone can assemble and adapt for their experiments, or an open source environmental sensor for monitoring air or water quality.

University of Utrecht, Wageningen University & Research), there is no national initiative for open research hardware in the Netherlands. This will be the first funding to increase and stimulate coordination on the topic of open research hardware in the Netherlands.

Budget

€1.5M in 2027.

2.4 Citizen Science Hubs

Why

In 2025, Open Science NL launched the **Citizen Science Hubs** call to strengthen institutional knowledge, expertise, and support for citizen science, including science communication, within Dutch research organisations. The call's aim was to establish dedicated flagship hubs that served as centralised points of contact for expertise, resources, and infrastructure to effectively coordinate and support citizen science activities. Nine consortia formed and requested funding from Open Science NL in that Call for proposals.

The 2025 call contributed to the growing recognition of institutional citizen science agendas and highlighted the pressing need for additional capacity building. Support for citizen science is still taking shape and is in need for further professionalisation. The collaborations that emerged from the first call provide a unique opportunity to build up in a follow-up support programme, which could significantly enhance capacity building efforts. Open Science NL therefore proposes a second funding round in 2025.

What

The second **Citizen Science Hubs** call maintains a similar structure as the first round, requiring collaboration among research organisations. The focus on academic capacity building remains central, as does the requirement for in-kind contributions. The new round further ensures a balanced geographical and thematic distribution of hubs, complementing the hubs from the first round of the call. The established hubs from the first call will be encouraged and facilitated to mentor the hubs funded in the second round, thereby supporting the participation of both emerging and developing hubs in this round.

Funding instrument

Call for proposals with mentoring elements or a designated mentoring programme.

Eligibility

All eligible knowledge institutions which have not received funding in the first round are eligible to apply for establishing a hub. Those knowledge institutions which received funding in the Citizen Science Hubs call 2024/2025, can apply for mentorship activities.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

In the Netherlands there is no financial support programme to strengthen citizen science capacity at research organisations besides the Citizen Science Hubs call organised by Open Science NL in 2024.

Budget

€2.5M in 2027.

2.5 AI and Open Science

Why

In recent years, there has been significant investment in and attention for Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools. These developments have had a major impact on open science and the open science community. Open science community members have been grappling with questions such as when it is ethically justified to use (commercial) AI tools; how to make datasets AI-ready; how AI tools could help to clean and validate incomplete or noisy data (a challenge pertinent for example in citizen science data); how to address copyright issues surrounding data used for AI model training or how to ensure that the infrastructures supporting AI models in research are open and sustainable. Furthermore, there are concerns about the openness of AI tools and their reliance on FAIR datasets and the adherence to the CARE principles. These are just some of the unresolved issues in this area.

A wide range of tools, guidelines and resources addressing these questions already exists, and there is considerable expertise within the community. However, these resources and this expertise are scattered, resulting in a lack of shared awareness of current challenges and opportunities, bad and good practices across the community.

What

This initiative aims to collect the concerns, questions and requests for information and tools raised by the open science community at large, as well as to do an initial mapping of the relevant resources, tools and expertise

already available to enable identifying existing gaps. This will be achieved through broad community and expert consultations, events and workshops. The outcomes will be documented in a publicly available report to inform future developments in this area and provide concrete recommendations for Open Science NL and the open science community.

Financial instrument

Procurement.

Eligibility

Procurement to the most suitable organisation.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

There has been a lot of initiatives, projects and tools developed pertaining to AI, ethics of AI, transparency of AI etc. Furthermore, there is already a lot of expertise on the topics or AI transparency. The purpose of this assignment is not to develop any new tools or guidelines, but to map out existing expertise, networks and resources specifically against the Dutch open science community needs (hence, this will focus specifically on overlap between AI and open science).

Budget

€150K in 2026.

3 Empowering communities

Three initiatives in this work programme focus on empowering communities, which is essential to make open science practices normative.

3.1 Community-led Citizen Science: exploration grant

Why

When society is actively involved in research and innovation, the outcomes become more relevant, and science itself can become further democratised. In community-led research or community-led citizen science, citizens determine the research and knowledge agenda, initiate and conduct the research⁹. To properly support such research, projects should be driven by questions from local communities. This challenges current processes and frameworks, which are set in place for research driven by research organisations.

Research councils have difficulties supporting community-led research, as their grant rules do not permit direct funding to civic organisations. Open Science NL therefore collaborates with NWO's Dutch Research Agenda (NWA) to explore how such grass-roots research can be best supported.

Open Science NL has solicited advice on how to facilitate equal collaborations between academic organisations and local communities (Open Science NL work programme 2024-2025, initiative 4.2) which has informed the setup of a pilot for community-led research (currently being investigated within the NWA).

In addition to research projects, the advice calls for laying the groundwork for appropriate (soft) infrastructures: capacity and community building. At present, collaborations between local communities and researchers are often fragmented. Moreover, the specific capacity needs of both academics and local communities in participatory research remain insufficiently documented^{10 11 12}. In addition to its collaboration with the NWA programme, Open Science NL proposes to invest in defining the soft infrastructure needed to facilitate, sustain and maximise the reach and impact of community-led research.

What

Open Science NL proposes to extend the existing Citizen Science NL (CS-NL) network with representative bodies of local civic communities (e.g. citizen collectives). This is essential because while the network comprises practitioners and researchers from public and private organisations, representatives

⁹ Hacking, N., Lewis, J. & Evans, R. Mapping Approaches to 'Citizen Science' and 'Community Science' and Everything In-between: The Evolution of New Epistemic Territory?. *Minerva* 62, 549-572 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-024-09529-z>

¹⁰ Interim report advice for NWO: pre-call trajectory Citizen Science: <https://zenodo.org/records/15703423>

¹¹ Advice for NWO: final advice pre-call trajectory Citizen Science: <https://zenodo.org/records/17232298>

¹² Van Gestel, E.C.E., Nagelhout, G.E., Mogendorff, K., Mogana, M., Rougour, M., Remmers, G., Wolkorte, R., Wildevuur, S. (2025). *De Kracht van Burgerwetenschap in het gezondheidsdomein*. Enschede, Breda, Amsterdam: Universiteit Twente, Avans Hogeschool, Mijn Data|Onze Gezondheid.

from local communities – such as citizen collectives – have limited representation. Ensuring that citizen collectives are part of the CS-NL network will help build collaborations and thus facilitating the creation of shared research agendas. Furthermore, this programme will also specifically focus on identifying the capacity needs of civic community organisations for effectively collaborating with researchers. The design of this assignment is inspired by [the UKRI's 'community research network fund'](#) and [community-led research programmes](#).

Funding instrument

Procurement.

Eligibility

Procurement to the most suitable organisation. The applicants will have to represent local communities, such as intermediary groups for citizen collectives or similar organisations with direct links to existing social initiatives.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

The funder ZonMw experiments with citizen-driven or community-led research in calls like ['Onderzoek voor en door jongeren'](#) and ['Samen aan de Hartslag'](#). UK's funding organisation [UKRI is extensively investing in community-led research programmes](#).

Budget

€250K in 2026.

3.2 Open Science Festival

Why

The National Open Science Festival has been organised annually since 2021, and Open Science NL has been organising the festival since 2024. The festival gives researchers, professional support staff, policy makers and other stakeholders interested in open science the opportunity to connect with peers and to learn about open science practices, policies and implementations. The event is also an important vehicle for Open Science NL to engage with the community and present its work and achievements. Given the important role of the event for empowering and engaging with the community and making open science practices more visible, the popularity of the event, and since it is the only national level event that covers all aspects of open science, it is proposed to continue to support the organisation of the festival on a yearly basis.

What

The National Open Science Festival will be organised annually as the flagship national event on open science for researchers, professional support staff, policy makers and anyone else interested in open science. It will be free of charge to attend. Open Science NL will oversee the organisation and programme of the festival, involving the community and outsourcing certain elements to an external partner. Each year, a university of applied sciences, a university, a research institute, or a combination of these, acts as host and co-organiser.

Funding instrument

Not applicable – this funding will be managed directly by Open Science NL.

Eligibility

Not applicable – this funding will be managed directly by Open Science NL.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

The National Open Science Festival brings together all stakeholders and initiatives interested in open science and facilitates knowledge and experience sharing by connecting people and organisations. It is unique in its kind and directly related to the engagement activities of Open Science NL. It has proven to be a valuable place to gather community feedback.

Budget

€100K in 2026 and €100K in 2027.

3.3 Open Science Meetings

Why

The goal of this programme is to stimulate community engagement in open science. In the Open Science NL work programme 2024-2025, two successful rounds of this Call for proposals were run, funding 40 events in 2024 and another 32 in 2025. The initiative proved both effective and popular: in 2025 the budget was already exhausted in August. It is therefore proposed not only to continue the **Open Science Meetings** calls in the work programme 2026-2027, but also to increase the annual budget from €300K to €400K.

What

The proposed instrument will allow communities to apply for funding to organise small-scale meetings on an open science topic of their own choosing. This could also include emerging topics pertaining to open science, such as AI, digital sovereignty, open research hardware etc. Proposals submitted by communities will be assessed by the Open Science NL office solely against administrative criteria. Proposals can be submitted at any time and successful applications will be funded on a first come, first served basis. The instrument is a continuation of the current Open Science NL **Open Science Meetings** call.

Funding instrument

First come, first served Call for proposals.

Eligibility

Researchers and professional support staff affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions, as well as the following other organisations: museums, (public) libraries, patient organisations and citizen collectives.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

The aim of this initiative is to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between and within communities, organisations, and initiatives related to open science, and it remains unique in the Netherlands at present.

Budget

€400K in 2026 and €400K in 2027.

4 Incentives

Two initiatives presented in this chapter are related to incentives, which are crucial for motivating and rewarding behaviours that prioritise openness, collaboration, and transparency.

4.1 Making Research Outputs FAIR

Why

There are research outputs which could be of value to the community at large but are currently not FAIR and open, and thus the value cannot be realised. Such outputs could include, for example:

- “Legacy” datasets – valuable datasets, sometimes been collected over many years, which were never made FAIR and open due to lack of FAIR practices at the time;
- Datasets which cannot be made open due to their sensitive nature;
- Essential research software which is not reusable (lacking documentation, an explicit licence etc);
- Hardware designs, or AI models, which are not open and FAIR;
- Non-traditional research outputs where practices of making outputs open and FAIR are not yet so common.

Note that these are just examples, and the list above is not exhaustive. Making such outputs as open and FAIR as possible could stimulate their reuse and impact and provide an incentive for making outputs FAIR and open. Furthermore, NWO’s past Call for proposals **Open Science Fund** revealed that there is a

need and willingness within the community to make research outputs FAIR, which can be effectively addressed with small grants.

What

The aim of these funding initiative is to incentivise making research outputs as open and FAIR as possible. Applicants can apply for a maximum of €50K to make research outputs of value to the community open and FAIR. The applicants will be also required to document and reflect on the steps that they have taken to make their outputs as open and FAIR as possible and propose a plan to share their lessons learnt with the community to maximise the impact of the award. The funding will be split between the different domains of research. total budget will be split across all the academic disciplines to facilitate even participation. Funding will be awarded to eligible applications on a first come, first served basis until the budget for each domain is exhausted.

Funding instrument

First come, first served Call for proposals.

Eligibility

Researchers and professional support staff affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives?

The NWO **Open Science Fund** used to fund similar projects, but it is suspended, resulting in a big gap and an unaddressed demand. Funding from Open Science NL could address this gap.

Budget

€2.85M in 2026.

4.2 Replication Studies

Why

Between 2016 and 2019, NWO and ZonMw ran a Replication Studies Programme with a total budget of €3M, allocated across three funding rounds. The goals of this programme were the support of replication studies, to make them more common, but also to learn how funding agencies may work towards incorporating funding for replication studies in their regular funding instruments. Its mid-term evaluation was positive, but the evaluation committee noted that it was still too soon to integrate replication studies in existing funding instrument ('mainstreaming'). The committee therefore recommended to continue dedicated funding for replication. **The Replication Studies** call within the Open Science NL work programme 2024–2025 was open to all academic disciplines and adopted a more nuanced definition of replication to encourage applications from fields where replicability is less common or exact replications are difficult. Given the significant interest in the previous call, a second round of the Open Science NL **Replication Studies** programme is proposed.

What

The next round of the replication studies programme will be very similar to the previous round. The call will be open to researchers from all disciplines, excluding researchers funded in the 2025 call, to enhance the variety in projects and researchers funded through the programme. We will explore a more efficient and thorough assessment procedure, to improve on the procedure of the 2025 call. This may involve an assessment procedure where applicants also act as reviewers (distributed peer review) as applied in several NWO calls. Care will be taken to ensure a good distribution of projects over disciplines, to widen the discussion on replication methodology and promote the methodological discussions where this is needed.

Funding format

Call for proposals.

Eligibility

Researchers affiliated with eligible knowledge institutions.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

This initiative builds directly on the previous **Replication Studies** round by Open Science NL and the earlier NWO **Replication Studies** programmes and their evaluation. Offering funding for replication studies is still a unique initiative.

Budget

€3M in 2027.

5 Monitoring and evaluation

There is one dedicated initiative pertaining to monitoring and evaluation of open science, which aims to provide evidence of progress, identify barriers, and guide improvements to ensure that openness becomes effectively and sustainably implemented.

5.1 Open Science Monitor

Why

Monitoring open science is crucial for ensuring transparency, measuring progress and impact, and informing decision-making and policy. Of similar importance is creating evaluation mechanisms for open science practices. In the first Open Science NL work programme 2024-2025 a first step was taken by means of a tender procedure which led to a project to establish a framework with context-specific indicators (what to measure) and methodologies (how to measure) for monitoring open science and developing mechanisms for evaluation purposes. Part of this first step has been a broad community consultation to develop a monitoring framework, as well as the delivery of a minimal viable product of an online dashboard.

What

Building on this, the goal for this funding instrument is to:

1. consolidate the recommendations and outcomes of the first phase, and
2. to develop a sustainable, transparent and inclusive (e.g., outputs and engagements) open science monitoring and evaluation

infrastructure for the Netherlands, which also takes into account the outcomes and recommendations of other relevant projects, such as **Recognising and Rewarding Open Science** (initiative 5.5 of the Open Science NL Work Programme 2024-2025).

Funding instrument

This project will most likely be funded through a European tender for a project lasting max. 4 years. However, other options will be investigated.

Eligibility

Any organisation able to meet the requirements/eligibility criteria can participate. Applicants must have experience and a proven track record in the monitoring and evaluation of academic (open) research practices.

How Open Science NL initiative differs from other initiatives

This project aligns with the initiatives to monitor the progress of open science being taken in many countries, including France, Ireland and, at the European level, for example by the EOSC Association. This project is expected to build on the recommendations of international organisations and developments, such as the UNESCO Open Science Monitoring Initiative (OSMI) and CoARA.

Budget

€1M in 2027.

Annex 1

Mapping to NPOS Ambition document and to the outcomes of community consultation

OSNL work programme 2026-2027	NPOS Ambition document	Community consultation
1.1 Open Science Infra-structure	<p>Objective 1.4 – ‘In 2030, Citizen Science-generated data, knowledge, insights and practices are easily gathered, hosted and aggregated via data infrastructures and technical tools’;</p> <p>Objective 3.2 – ‘In 2027, the digital infrastructure for scientific publications and metadata is sustainable and preferably open, and supports publication, (re-)use and analysis by anyone’;</p> <p>Objective 3.4 – ‘In 2030, there will be a public platform for scientific publications, that allows everyone in the Netherlands to re-use global scholarly output for their professional and societal engagement practices’;</p> <p>Objective 4.4 – ‘In 2027, Dutch FAIR research services and infrastructure are efficiently organised and connected, closely linked to the European digital infrastructure’;</p> <p>Objective 4.7 – ‘In 2030, the Dutch open science community has access to a robust, cost-effective, and sustainable research software ecosystem’.</p>	The importance of open and integrated science infrastructure has been stressed in all community consultation workshops and in consultations with advisory panels.
1.2 Improving access to sensitive data	Objective 4.5 – ‘In 2027 (...) Dutch stakeholders have harmonised the conditions for access to sensitive data. There is a national data governance expert platform to design and implement nationally harmonised policies for access to FAIR data, with specific attention to sensitive data’.	The importance of improved access to sensitive data has been pointed out during community consultations and in discussions with the FAIR data advisory panel.

OSNL work programme 2026-2027	NPOS Ambition document	Community consultation
2.1 Training for open science infrastructure sustainability	In the NPOS 2020 Ambition document the need for sustainability of infrastructures is stressed in multiple places and across several objectives and recommendations. The term “sustainable” is mention 16 times and the term “sustainability” 6 times.	The need for securing sustainability for crucial open science infrastructure has been raised during both community consultations and during the discussions with advisory panels for all programme lines.
2.2 Mobility and development programme	Objective 4.6 – ‘In 2030, a professional community of well-trained data stewards has been established and there is enough (...) capacity (...) to facilitate making digital scientific objects FAIR.’ Objective 4.9 – ‘In 2030, there is sufficient capacity and expertise of research support staff to enable the use of open research software.’	The need for training and mobility programme has been raised during both community consultations and during the discussions with all advisory panels.
2.3 Open research hardware network	Not applicable – open research hardware has not been included in the NPOS2030 agenda. It is an emerging topic of importance to the community.	The need for support for open research hardware has been signalled during both the community consultations, and discussions in the Open Research Software advisory panel.

OSNL work programme 2026-2027	NPOS Ambition document	Community consultation
2.4 Citizen Science Hubs	<p>Objective 1.1 – ‘In 2025, RPOs, RFOs, and HEIs recognize the value and impact of Societal Engagement approaches to science, policy and society. Participatory and inclusive research practices are embedded’</p> <p>Objective 1.5 – ‘In 2030, capacity for Societal Engagement has been built up [...] with dedicated support [...] within institutions’.</p>	<p>Several topics which have been raised during community consultations are addressed in this initiative, such as “recognition of citizen science and driving a culture change at research organisations” or “training and capacity building in Citizen Science, participatory research, science communication and connected areas”</p>
2.5 AI and Open Science	<p>AI has not been included in the NPOS2030 agenda. It is an emerging topic of importance to the community. However, the vision, and the objectives 4 and 4.1 are about the necessity of making data machine-actionable.</p>	<p>This has been raised by the FAIR Data advisory panel, the Open Science NL Steering Board and the Open Science NL Strategy Council.</p>
3.1 Community-led Citizen Science pilot	<p>Objective 1.2 – ‘In 2025, there is a strong and active national Citizen Science practitioners network that (...) facilitates knowledge exchange, transdisciplinary collaboration, the further development of best practice and new innovations, and the formation of new multi-stakeholder initiatives across a wide range of domains.’</p> <p>Objective 4 – ‘Diversity, equity, and inclusiveness are crucial for the success of Open Science’</p>	<p>Several topics which have been raised during community consultations are addressed in this initiative, such as ‘support for citizen science outside of academia’ and ‘knowledge exchange’, ‘recognition of citizens in form of (financial) compensation, training/ learning etc.’ or ‘supporting grass-roots developments (establishing civic citizen science hubs)’.</p>

OSNL work programme 2026-2027	NPOS Ambition document	Community consultation
3.2 Open Science Festival	<p>Objective 0.2 - 'In 2023, national Open Science-related networks are more closely connected to each other, and are in the position to influence, collaborate with and benefit from the NPOS.'</p> <p>Objective 0.3 - 'In 2023, there is broad awareness of Open Science practices at all levels (strategic, tactical and operational) within the Dutch knowledge institutions. There are funding instruments that focus on collecting, developing and sharing examples/ good practices of Open Science practices and processes, both within academia and with societal partners.'</p> <p>Objective 0.6 - 'There is continuous effort in raising and maintaining awareness on Open Science through events (e.g. the Netherlands National Open Science Festival: MEET SHARE INSPIRE CARE).'</p>	<p>The Open Science Festival is highly valued by the community, as reflected in the positive feedback consistently received from delegates. Open Science NL also uses the festival as an opportunity to consult and engage with the community.</p>
3.3 Open Science Meetings	<p>Objective 0.2 - 'In 2023, national Open Science-related networks are more closely connected to each other, and are in the position to influence, collaborate with and benefit from the NPOS'.</p>	<p>The meetings have been valued by the community. Many of the awarded meetings themselves can be seen as an event where community consultation takes place.</p>
4.1 Making Research Outputs FAIR	<p>Guiding principle 2 - 'Scientific outputs and processes must be as open as possible, but as restricted as necessary';</p> <p>Objective 3.3 - 'In 2030, all scholarly output from publicly financed knowledge institutions (...) is freely and sustainably available and reusable under an open licence.'</p>	<p>The need for funding for making research outputs FAIR has been identified as a gap during community consultations and by the Open Science Fund applicants.</p>

OSNL work programme 2026-2027	NPOS Ambition document	Community consultation
4.1 Making Research Outputs FAIR	<p>Objective 4 – ‘In 2030, products of and for knowledge creation, like data and software, are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), and open.’</p> <p>Objective 4.3 – ‘In 2025, 40% of the digital scientific objects and corresponding meta-information in RPOs has been made FAIR (...); in 2030, this will be 75%.’</p> <p>Objective 4.5 – ‘In 2027, it will be possible to share FAIR research objects (‘as open as possible, as restricted as necessary’)’</p> <p>Objective 4.10 – ‘In 2030, all research based on the use of research software (including data, publications, methods, and analyses) is transparent, verifiable, reproducible, and reusable.’</p>	<p>The need for funding for making research outputs FAIR has been identified as a gap during community consultations and by the Open Science Fund applicants.</p>
4.2 Replication Studies	<p>Objective 2.1 – ‘In 2025, replication and reproducibility of scientific claims are recognized and rewarded as crucial parts of the research process. Good practices are collected and shared, and dedicated funding instruments have been established for replication and reproduction’.</p>	<p>During the preparation of the first OSNL Replication Studies call extensive feedback was gathered from the research community which informed the design of this Call for proposals.</p>
5.1 Open Science Monitor	<p>Objective 0.4 – ‘In 2025, open science practices and interventions are continuously and thoroughly monitored and assessed to understand their impact’.</p>	<p>The need for adequate monitoring and evaluation has been signalled not only during community consultations and discussions in the advisory panels, but has been also a topic of various workshops organised by the community. This is also one of the tasks of OSNL as determined by the covenant.</p>

Annex 2

Allocated budget

The table below outlines the budget to be allocated in years 2026-2027, in millions of euros (€M).

Cost item	2026	2027
Implementation costs	1.3M	1.3M
Costs of external assessment of funding instruments	0.15M	0.15M
1 Infrastructure	2026	2027
1.1 Open Science Infrastructure		17.5M
1.2 Improving access to sensitive data	1.1M	1.4M
2 Capacity building	2026	2027
2.1 Training for open science infrastructure sustainability	0.25M	
2.2 Mobility and development programme	1M	
2.3 Open research hardware network		1.5M
2.4 Citizen Science Hubs		2.5M
2.5 AI and Open Science	0.15M	
3 Empowering communities	2026	2027
3.1 Community-led Citizen Science: exploration grant	0.25M	
3.2 Open Science Festival	0.1M	0.1M
3.3 Open Science Meetings	0.4M	0.4M
4 Incentives	2026	2027
4.1 Making Research Outputs FAIR	2.85M	
4.2 Replication Studies		3M
5 Monitoring and evaluation	2026	2027
5.1 Open Science Monitor		1M
Total	7.55M	28,85M
Total for both years	36.4M	

Open Science NL / NWO

Laan van Nieuw Oost Indië 300
2593 CE Den Haag

Mail address

Postbus 93461

2509 AL Den Haag

www.openscience.nl

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